

CORE BEHAVIORAL COMPETENCIES AND MOTIVATIONAL STRATEGIES: INPUTS TO TEACHER'S PERFORMANCE

CLEO MAY VELASCO TUNAY

16-fs-em-319@lspu.edu.ph

ORCID No. 0000-0002-8482-2479

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The aim of this research is to determine the relationship of Core Behavioral Competencies and Motivational Strategies: Inputs to Teacher's Performance. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions: (1) How do the respondents perceive the following core behavioral competencies in terms of self-management, professionalism and ethics, results focus, teamwork, service orientation, and innovation? (2) How do the respondents perceive the motivational strategy in terms of recognition, reward system, positive competition, give responsibility, self-reflection, and mentoring? (3) What is the level of teachers' performance in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, assessment, and reporting, and plus factor? (4) Is there a significant relationship between core behavioral competencies and teachers' performance? (5) Is there a significant relationship between motivational strategy and teachers' performance? The findings of the study: the mean perception of the respondents on core behavioral competencies in terms of self-management, professionalism and ethics, results focus, teamwork, service orientation, and innovation have descriptive interpretation of "always". The mean perception of the respondents on the motivational strategies in terms of recognition, reward system, positive competition, give responsibility, self-reflection, and mentoring has also descriptive interpretation of "always". The level of teachers' performance in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, assessment, and reporting, and plus factor are "very satisfactory". Based on the findings posited in the study, the following are hereby concluded that (1) there is no significant relationship between core behavioral competencies and teachers' performance. (2) There is no significant relationship between motivational strategy and teachers' performance.

Keywords: Core Behavioral Competencies, Motivational Strategies, Teacher's Performance